

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A HARMONIOUSLY DEVELOPED PERSONALITY.

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Abstract. This article is about education and its role in society. Education presupposes the civic and social responsibility of each person. Education is a means of emotional integration to ensure unity. We cannot do useful mental work without any knowledge. Education is an important part of human development. Education is a means to achieve peace, justice, freedom and equality for every person. Therefore, education is necessary for everyone. There is no better life without education.

Keywords: education, types of Education, opinion, formal, informal, opportunity

Аннотация. Эта статья об образовании и его роли в обществе. Образование предполагает гражданскую и социальную ответственность за всех. Образование является средством эмоциональной интеграции для обеспечения единства. Мы не можем выполнять какую-либо полезную умственную работу без какой-либо информации. Образование является важной частью человеческого развития. Образование – это средство достижения мира, справедливости, свободы и равенства для всех во всем мире. Так что образование очень необходимо для всех. Без образования нет хорошей жизни.

Ключевые слова: образование, виды образования, мнение, формальное, неформальное, возможность

Introduction.

Great importance is attached to strengthening the education system, bringing it in line with the requirements of the time in our Republic. At the same time, it is important that the system of training, training and education of specialists is closely linked to the requirements of reforms. The training of qualified personnel capable of meeting modern requirements, education based on state requirements and the improvement of all its structures is one of the urgent tasks facing us. Currently, life itself dictates the need for reforms in all spheres of our country, changes in people's worldview, and the training of mature and time-appropriate specialists.

Literature analysis and methods.

Education is a purposeful activity aimed at achieving certain goals, such as the transfer of knowledge or the development of skills and character traits. These goals may include developing understanding, rationality, kindness, and honesty. Various researchers emphasize the role of critical thinking in separating education from upbringing. Some theorists believe that education leads to the improvement of the student, while others prefer a useless definition of the term. In a slightly different sense, education can refer not only to the process, but also to the product of this process: the mental states and inclinations of educated people.

The education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes the following:¹

- ✓ state and non-state educational institutions that implement educational programs in accordance with state standards;
- ✓ scientific and pedagogical institutions that carry out research work necessary to ensure the functioning and development of the education system;
- ✓ public administration bodies in the field of education, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations subordinate to them.

The reforms in the field of continuing education include the following:

- development of various types of state and non-state educational institutions;

¹ R.Ahliddinov "Uzluksiz ta'limda pedagogik boshqaruv masalalari" T: 2012. 25-b

- ensuring the transition from compulsory general secondary education to specialized secondary, vocational;

-training, retraining and advanced training of personnel of new professions and specialties, including personnel of the management system associated with the widespread development of advanced technologies, structural changes in the economy, the expansion of foreign investment, the development of entrepreneurship, small and private business;

- improvement of the education management system, development of forms of public administration, regionalization of educational institutions;

- creation and implementation of a system of objective assessment of the quality of the educational process and personnel training;

- development and implementation of integrated mechanisms for the integration of continuing education with science and production;

- creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions for obtaining education in the native language in places of compact residence of persons who are not indigenous peoples;

Interdisciplinarity is a condition for the unity of education and upbringing, encouraging students to apply knowledge in everyday life.

The integrative lesson is considered one of the much better developed forms. The main descriptive characteristics of an integrative lesson are the following:

- Synthesis of the activities of two or more teachers and etc.;
- Its pedagogical capabilities are revealed;
- Formation of knowledge in combination with the skills of their application in practice;
- communication skills, increased interest in learning, loss of fear, self-doubt.
- synthesis of the studied material, theoretical and industrial training; mutual synthesis of general education disciplines;

Discussion.

Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out in the types of preschool education, general secondary education, secondary special, vocational education, higher education, postgraduate education, advanced training and retraining of personnel, extracurricular education.

Preschool education is usually carried out through state and non-state preschool institutions, by creating short-term groups. This training is conducted in the family, kindergarten and other educational institutions, regardless of the form of ownership, at the age of six to seven years and is aimed at forming the child's personality in a healthy and mature way, prepared for school.

General secondary education usually pursues the goal of forming the foundations of literacy, knowledge and skills necessary for obtaining general secondary education, giving the necessary amount of knowledge, developing independent thinking skills, organizational skills and practical experience, career guidance at the initial stage and choosing the next stage of training.²

Secondary specialized, vocational education is carried out at an Academic lyceum or a vocational college. Its main goal is to ensure the intensive development of students' intellectual abilities, their acquisition of deep, differentiated and career-oriented knowledge, deep development of professional inclinations, skills and abilities of students, obtaining one or more specialties in selected professions.³

Higher education is represented in higher educational institutions (universities, academies, institutes and other educational institutions of higher education). The main purpose of higher education is to provide in-depth knowledge in one of the areas of higher education (bachelor's degree) or a specific specialty (master's degree).⁴

² Инновационный менеджмент: Учебник / Под. ред. Горфинкеля В. Я – М.: Вузовский учебник, 2020. 15-б

Postgraduate education is aimed at meeting the needs of society in scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, which is carried out in higher educational institutions and research institutions (doctoral studies, independent research).⁵

Education originated as the transmission of cultural heritage from generation to generation. Today, educational goals are increasingly embracing new ideas, such as students' free participation in lessons, skills needed by modern society, and complex professional skills.⁶

Types of education are usually divided into formal and informal. Formal education is carried out in educational institutions and educational institutions, structured in accordance with the goals and objectives of training, and training is usually carried out under the guidance of a teacher. In many regions, formal education is compulsory up to a certain age and is divided into stages of education, such as kindergarten, primary school and secondary school. Non-formal education arises as a supplement or alternative to formal education, which can be structured according to education agreements, but in a more flexible manner and usually in a community-based, workplace-based or civil society setting. Finally, informal learning takes place in everyday life, in the family, any experience that has a formative influence on thinking, feelings or behavior, whether unintentional or intentional, can be considered educational. In practice, there is a continuum from highly formalized to very informal, and informal learning can occur in all three contexts, for example, home schooling can be classified as informal or informal depending on the structure. Regardless of the purpose, teaching methods include teaching, learning, storytelling, discussion, and focused research. The teaching method is called pedagogy. Education is supported by various philosophies, theories and empirical research programs. There are efforts to reform education, such as improving the quality and effectiveness of learning through relevance in the lives of students and effective problem solving in modern or future society, or through evidence-based learning methodology. The right to education is

recognized by some Governments and the United Nations. In our country, every citizen has the right to education.^{7,8}

There is usually a belief that education is the basis for comprehensive development. Life is based on progress, and development and growth are life. If we consider this point of view from the point of view of education, then we can conclude that education is the comprehensive development of a person's personality. Thus, education is nothing but the comprehensive development of a person's personality. Education is the process of teaching a harmonious personality. Therefore, education is necessary for everyone.

Results.

Education implies civic and social responsibility for all. Education is a tool of emotional integration to ensure unity. We cannot perform useful mental work without any knowledge. Education is an important part of human development. Education is a means to achieve peace, justice, freedom and equality for all. Thus, education is necessary for everyone. There is no good life without education. Education develops a person's intelligence, skills and allows him to open the door to opportunities. Education ensures future progress. Education also directs the undeveloped capabilities, attitudes, interests, requirements and needs of a person into the desired channels. A person can explore and change the environment through education according to their needs. In a democratic country, education is necessary for all citizens. Democratic mechanisms cannot function well if all citizens do not have education. Equality of educational opportunities has been ensured in our country. It is necessary to take advantage of this opportunity. It is very important that the owners of families receive education and upbringing, so that families with a small link in society are strong, so that children develop as harmonious personalities in the family. Education is an important factor of success, character building and a full and happy life. True education develops a person into a true person, mentally perfect.

It is no secret that in our country there are ample opportunities for conducting non-governmental organizational forms of education. Nevertheless, the management of its organizational processes according to a certain pattern is under the control of the government.

- Public administration bodies in the field of education monitor compliance with the legislation on education in non-state educational institutions;
- that in case of violation by non-governmental educational institutions of the legislation on education, the bodies accredited by them have the right to suspend their activities in accordance with the legislation;
- it is noted that admission to non-state educational institutions is carried out in accordance with the procedure and deadlines established for state educational institutions.

The reforms in the field of continuing education include:

- development of various types of state and non-state educational institutions;
- ensuring the transition from compulsory general secondary education to specialized secondary, vocational;
- training, retraining and advanced training of personnel of new professions and specialties, including personnel of the management system associated with the widespread development of advanced technologies, structural changes in the economy, the expansion of foreign investment, the development of entrepreneurship, small and private business;
- improvement of the education management system, development of forms of public administration, regionalization of educational institutions;
- creation and implementation of a system of objective assessment of the quality of the educational process and personnel training;
- development and implementation of integrated mechanisms for the integration of continuing education with science and production;

- creation of organizational and pedagogical conditions for obtaining education in the native language in places of compact residence of persons who are not indigenous peoples.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of reforms carried out in the republic on the path of radical changes in the education system and the creation of comprehensive conditions for a deep understanding by the general public of the essence of the documents adopted in this direction is defined as the most urgent task of employees of public administration, law enforcement agencies, educational institutions. In a word, when organizing the educational process, it becomes important to have the state as an institution of management. Because, first of all, it becomes important to follow the standards and organize the learning process within the framework of the law. There is usually a belief that education is the basis for comprehensive development. Life is based on progress, and development and growth are life. If we consider this point of view from the point of view of education, then we can conclude that education is the comprehensive development of a person's personality. Thus, education is nothing but the comprehensive development of a person's personality. Education is the process of teaching a harmonious personality. Therefore, education is necessary for everyone.

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